

Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid Hydrolysis of Di-4-chloro-2,6 dimethylphenyl Orthophosphate

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THE acid hydrolysis of di-4-chloro-2,6 dimethylphenyl phosphate ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) in the acid range 0.5–6 M HCl at $98 \pm 0.5^\circ$ has been performed in 50% propionic acid–water mixture. The inorganic phosphate obtained during hydrolysis has been estimated colorimetrically by Allen's modified method¹. A rare kind of rate coefficients of pseudo-zero order have been calculated using integrated form of the corresponding rate equation². Two types of reactive species, neutral and conjugate acid are present and contribute to the overall rates.

Experimental

The diester has been synthesised by Auger and Dupuis method³. Both the parent phenol in benzene and $POCl_3$ (1 : 1 ratio) were stirred at 60° for ~9 h with the addition of pyridine (7 ml) at regular intervals. The yellow oily residue after treatment with NaOH and dilute HCl was recrystallised in CCl_4 , m.p. $220-24^\circ$ (Found : C, 51.50 ; H, 4.30. Calcd for : C, 51.21 ; H, 4.53 ; P, 8.27%).

Results and Discussion

The zero order rate coefficients for the hydrolysis of the diester show a constancy at 0.5–2 M HCl and then increase with an increase in acid molarity upto 4 M, and then decrease ($> 4 M$). The presence of the maximum (Table 1) shows the moderately basic character of the diester.

TABLE 1—CALCULATED AND OBSERVED ZERO ORDER RATE COEFFICIENTS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF DI-4-CHLORO-2,6-DIMETHYLPHENYL ORTHOPHOSPHATE AT 98° IN 50% PROPIONIC ACID WATER (v/v)

HCl M	$\times 10^5 K_N$ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	$\times 10^5 K_{H^+}$ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	$\times 10^5 K_0$ (Obsd)/ (Calcd.)
0.5	2.80	—	2.00 (2.80)
1.0	2.73	—	2.40 (2.73)
2.0	2.58	—	2.37 (2.58)
3.0	2.44	—	2.76 (2.44)
4.0	2.31	1.45	4.00 (3.76)
5.0	2.19	1.78	3.94 (3.97)
6.0	—	2.10	2.05 (2.10)

The effect of ionic strength⁴ has been studied using LiCl as an inert salt. The diester is not very sensitive to changing ionic strengths, so that the linear curves lie close to each other. It postulates two reactive species, the neutral and the mono-protonated. Salt effect for both these species is negative, due to decrease in magnitude of both the intercepts as well as the slopes with rise in μ . On the basis of these reactive species the calculated rates are obtained by applying

$$K_e = K_{H^+} C_{H^+} K_N \quad (1)$$

On further applying, the 2nd empirical term of the Debye-Huckel equation⁵ for each form, and modifying logarithmically,

$$\log K_{H^+} C_{H^+} = \log K_{H_0^+} + \log C_{H^+} + (-b'_H + \mu) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Similarly, } \log K_N = \log K_{N_0} + (-b'_N \mu) \quad (3)$$

where, K_{H^+} , $K_{H_0^+}$, K_N and K_{N_0} in equations (2) and (3) are specific acid-catalysed rates at that ionic strength, at zero ionic strength, specific neutral rates at that ionic strength and at zero ionic strength, respectively. Also, $b = b/2.303$. The -ve sign is used because the salt effect is negative. From the equations (2) and (3), rates for both the species have been calculated, and these resemble the K_0 (obsd.) upto 5 M. The rates above 5 M (conjugate acid form alone), however, deviate from the normal value, which is attributed to (i) the decreasing reactivity of the neutral form, (ii) negative ionic strength effect, and (iii) decrease in water activity. Thus, the rates beyond 5 M have been calculated by applying Bronsted–Bjerrum equation⁶,

$$K_e = K_{H_0^+} C_{H^+} \exp b_{H^+} \mu (a_{H_2O})^n \quad (4)$$

where, $(a_{H_2O})^n$ represents water activity term⁷. The value of n at 6 M has been calculated as 0.5.

Various correlation plots (figures not shown) like Hammett plot⁷ (0.24), Zücker–Hammett plot⁷ (0.71), Bunnett plots⁷ ($W=9.09$, $W^*=1.03$) and Bunnett and Olsen plot⁸ ($\phi=1.1$) postulate a bimolecular route of hydrolysis, i.e. show the involvement of a water molecule as second reaction partner in the slow step. Further involvement of a single water molecule to form the T.S is derived from Yates and McClelland plot⁹ ($r=0.97$).

The solvent-isotope effect, using 46.08% of D_2O shown the hydrolysis to be specific acid-catalysed type. The rates are lowered ($K_{D_2O}/K_{H_2O}=0.56$) due to the weaker nucleophilic character of D_2O than H_2O .

Arrhenius parameters¹⁰ are at 3 M : $E=14.59$ kcal mol⁻¹, $A=1.35 \times 10^8$ mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹, $-\Delta S^\ddagger=50.65$ e.u., $\Delta G^\ddagger=33.38$ kcal mol⁻¹; at 4 M : $E=27.36$ kcal mol⁻¹, $A=7.80 \times 10^{10}$ mols dm⁻³ s⁻¹, $-\Delta S^\ddagger=15.42$ e.u., $\Delta G^\ddagger=33.08$ kcal mol⁻¹.

The conjugate acid form has already been shown to hydrolyse bimolecularly by various correlation plots. However, the above parameters at 3 *M* and 4 *M*, together require both uni- and bi-molecular modes of hydrolyses for the major neutral form.

Solvent effect has been studied for both the reactive forms. The neutral species forms a transition state with the creation of charges in both the modes of hydrolyses, as depicted in (A) and (B) in Chart 1. Thus, the rates at 3 *M* are increased in more polar (60% of this solvent mixture) solvent.

Chart 1. (A) Unimolecular hydrolysis of the neutral form (I) of the diester involving P-O bond fission and (B) bimolecular hydrolysis of (I) involving P-O bond fission.

At 5 *M*, this solvent composition first converts the major neutral form into its conjugate acid form, which then hydrolyses bimolecularly via a transition state having dispersal of charge in it (Chart 2).

Chart 2. (C) Formation of conjugate acid form (II) from the neutral form (I) by a fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer, and (D) bimolecular hydrolysis of (II) involving P-O bond fission.

Concentration effect studies^{1,2} (Table 2) have postulated two types of orders, (i) with respect to time, *nt* is zero, using integrated rate equation and (ii) with respect to concentration, *nc* is 1.21 using Van't Hoff's differential method². Since, the order with respect to time is less than the order with

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF DI-4-CHLORO-2,6-DIMETHYLPHENYL ORTHOPHOSPHATE AT 98°

HCl <i>M</i>	Substrate Concn. $\times 10^4$ (<i>M</i>)	$\times 10^4 K_0$ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
2.0	2.5	1.21
2.0	5.0	2.37
4.0	2.5	9.33
4.0	5.0	4.00
4.0	7.5	4.77
6.0	2.5	1.60
6.0	5.0	2.05

respect to concentration, the reaction is taken to proceed with autocatalysis. A similar situation has been observed in gas-phase decomposition^{1,2} of neopentyl chloride. The study also involves an induction period^{1,3} (Fig. 1) and it is noted that the monoester (K_0 , 10⁻² min⁻¹ at 90°) formed during the course of hydrolysis of the diester, possibly

Fig. 1. Plot of induction period vs log acid molarity for the hydrolysis of the diester in acid region.

autocatalyses the reaction. An average induction period for acid hydrolysis is 34 h at 98°. The substituents^{1,4} play a significant role in this case. As seen from the comparative rate data (Table 3), this diester is the least reactive via its neutral form (2.40×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ min⁻¹ at 98°), whereas *p*-Cl is the most reactive (0.52×10^{-5} min⁻¹ at 80°) in the series travelled. This shows that the introduction

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF PHENYL PHOSPHATE DIESTERS VIA THEIR NEUTRAL (1 M) AND CONJUGATE ACID SPECIES (4 M)

Phenyl phosphate diesters	Temp. °C	(5 + log K_e)	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	Fission	($\sigma + \sigma_I + \rho$) ^g
Phenyl ^b	100	1.84	20.8	27.96	P-O [†]	0.0
<i>p</i> -Cl ^o	80	3.12	10.6	65.00	P-O	0.454
<i>p</i> -Br ^d	98	1.82	20.14	30.00	P-O	0.464
2,4-di-Cl ^d	98	2.49	16.60	33.90	P-O	2.494
<i>p</i> -Cl-O-MeO ^o	98	1.97	18.21	36.61	P-O	1.774
2,4,6-tri-Cl ^f	90	2.67	24.41	11.87	P-O	4.534
2,4,6-tri-Br ^o	98	2.66	26.08	7.09	P-O	4.944
This work						
<i>p</i> -Cl-2,6-di-Me	98	0.38	27.36 [‡] 14.59 [‡]	15.42	P-O	-1.666
6-Br-2,4-di-Cl ^h	90	2.70	33.72	-13.71	P-O	4.734

^o σ = Hammett substituent constant, σ_I = Inductive substituent constant, V = Charton's steric substituent constant; (Ref. 14). ^bRef. 6. ^oRef. 16. ^dRef. 17. ^eRef. 19. ^fRef. 20. ^gRef. 21. ^hRef. 22. [†]Fission confirmed. [‡]At 4 M HCl. [‡]At 3 M HCl.

of two O—Me groups in each aryl system in the present case decreases the reactivity due to their 'ortho effect'. Unimolecular hydrolysis is also responsible for this decrease. Another reason for the decrease in reactivity is the orientation of the two aryl nuclei, which being symmetrical are opposed to each other and hence the overall effect is equal and opposite in magnitude.

This diester is taken to hydrolyse with P—O bond fission as it follows an isokinetic relationship¹⁵ (figure not shown) with other similarly substituted diaryl esters (Table 3) and gives a β value equal to 423.1 K. This value being greater than the absolute experimental temperature (371 K) shows that the reaction is most probably governed by the energy of activation. This is supported by a low value of acid-catalysed rates ($K_H^\ddagger = 0.0067$ mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) too.

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Zinc Chloride Catalysed Condensation of Mesityl Oxide with Benzoylacetone

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BASE catalysed Michael condensations of β -diketones and β -ketoesters with α,β -unsaturated-carbonyl compounds are well known to yield products of the cyclohexenone type¹⁻¹⁰. It is further known that branching at α - and/or β -position of the α,β -unsaturated-carbonyl compounds inhibit Michael addition. Literature reveals that Michael condensation induced by acid catalysts has not attracted much attention as yet. This field, however, appears interesting specially for condensations involving highly alkylated α,β -unsaturated-carbonyl compounds.